

Minutes of the 56th Experimenters' Meeting

The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Thursday 21st January 2016

(This document was finalised on 24th June 2016)

Present:

(CB)	Mrs Caroline Bulpett ³	
(CG)	Dr Catherine Gaffard ³	
(CJW)	Dr Chris Walden ⁵	
(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{4,5}	Secretary
(DK)	Dr Dirk Klugmann ⁵	
(EGN)	Dr Emily Norton ⁶	
(GAP)	Dr Graham Parton ^{2,5}	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁶	Chair
(HMAR)	Dr Hugo Ricketts ⁶	
(KEW)	Miss Kate Winfield ^{2,5}	
(LD)	Mr Les Dean ^{1,4}	
(ZL)	Dr Zhihong Li ³	

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²Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA)

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⁵Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

⁶University of Manchester

Other abbreviations used in this document:

BLWP	Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
CEDA	Centre for Environmental Data Analysis
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAS	National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NLC	Noctilucent Cloud
PC	Personal Computer
RMS	Root Mean Square
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UT	Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

The minutes of the 55th meeting were accepted without corrections.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 51.6.1 DAH to determine an improved method of applying the horizontal wind θ_s compensation factor so that its contribution to random errors is minimised.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 53.3.2 DAH to review security measures for the MST Radar site and to make improvements where necessary.

ONGOING

DAH reported that most of his recent time had been devoted to getting operational software working again after the CEDA computer that he had been using was retired in August 2015. Consequently he had not been able to devote any time to the above 6 action items.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

GAP reported that these statistics constitute metadata and that CEDA already has a mechanism for storing such files. He suggested that DAH should check whether the Met Office wanted to place any access restrictions on the files.

ACTION ITEM 53.4.2 GAP and DAH to determine a way of providing retrospectively-determined data reliability details in a machine-readable format.

ONGOING

DAH and GAP reported that they had had a meeting to discuss the possible use of the CHARMe (Characterisation of metadata to enable high-quality climate applications and services) system. This is being developed for use by a range of organisations, including ECMWF and the Met Office, as a way of annotating datasets. GAP is not yet sure whether it will be appropriate in this context. GV emphasised that people wanting to analyse long-term datasets need to be able to do so without having to scrutinise daily plots looking for problems.

GV expressed his disappointment that so many action items were outstanding. LD suggested that maybe DAH could take on a vacation or year-in-industry student to help him to deal with some of these tasks.

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

GAP reported that 33 registered CEDA users had accessed the MSTRF dataset during the past 12 months. Surface wind data were the most popular in terms of the number of users, although version 0 MST radar data dominated in terms of the number of files downloaded. The users were mostly from atmospheric physics and engineering backgrounds and mostly from the UK. The number of people (both those registered with CEDA and anonymous ones) accessing the quick-look plots was 422. In the case of the registered users, the profile was quite similar to that of people accessing the data files.

The MSTRF dataset is covered by an Open Government License - <http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/> - which states that users must acknowledge the source of the data. Moreover, academic publishers are increasingly expecting authors to cite datasets and there are well-defined ways to do this. This is particularly easy if the datasets have been assigned DOIs (digital object identifiers). There are already mechanisms to do this for continually-expanding datasets. GV suggested that the MSTRF dataset would be ideal for DOI assignment since it is relatively stable. He suggested that this should be implemented when the next generation (version 4) signal processing is introduced. He asked GAP to report on the use of DOIs at the next meeting.

ACTION ITEM 56.3.1 GAP to report on how DOIs can be assigned to datasets at the 57th Experimenters' meeting.

NEW

3b) Electricity - DAH

There have been a few high-impact electricity problems over the past 6 months. There was a three and a half hour outage starting at 05:30 UT on Sunday 23rd August 2015. The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units can only maintain operations for approximately 20 minutes following a loss of supply. The PCs responsible for running the radar (julius) and processing the data (claudius) restarted automatically when the electricity supply was restored. However, the one responsible for acquiring Campbell Scientific and laser ceilometer data (gaius) had to wait for LD to be on site the following day. DAH tried to remotely restart the MST radar at 12:40 UT on the 23rd, but noticed that the beam pointing direction was not changing between dwells. Consequently he stopped the radar 30 minutes later, deleted the recent spectral files, rebooted the beam steering PC (tiberius), and restarted the radar at 13:45 UT. He blocked the transfer of data to the Met Office until 15:30 UT, when he was satisfied that everything was working correctly.

A loss of power just after 09:00 UT on 30th September 2015 turned out to be caused by a problem within the site. This was established by an engineer from the local distribution company who visited the site during the morning. LD returned in the afternoon with members of Aberystwyth University's Estates team. They traced the problem to a failed section of cable that had connected the output of the voltage optimisation unit to the bungalow. Its rated capacity was found to be too low for the current being drawn through it. LD suspected that the contractors who had installed the voltage optimisation unit a few years previously were responsible for installing this section of cable. The University's Estates team called out a local electrician to carry out emergency repairs and the MST radar was back in operation by 14:45 UT.

The battery packs for UPS units TX1 and TX5 failed self tests on 14th October 2015. Moreover, the output from the TX5 unit did not resume following the test, which led to the transmitter for antenna sector E being out of action. The battery pack for unit TX1 was replaced on 23rd October. However, owing to the supplier running out of stock, there was a delay of several weeks before any additional battery packs were delivered. During this period there were more UPS problems. On 28th October unit TX3 repeat-

edly alternated between reporting a battery problem and normal operations. It failed to resume its output after a brief (~ 1 s) disruption to the mains supply at 20:40 UT on Friday 6th November 2015. Since it was powering the MST radar's phase synchronisation unit, radar operations ceased. LD happened to be away from Aberystwyth over this weekend and so normal radar operations were not resumed until his return on the Monday (9th) morning. UPS unit TXB failed a self test on 23rd December 2015. After a brief (~ 1 s) disruption to the mains supply at 04:05 UT on 6th January 2016, units TXB and Beamform failed to switch to battery power. This was a surprise since they both passed self tests a few hours later.

3c) Telecommunications

There were no problems during the previous 6 months.

3d) Miscellaneous

GV reported on the National Capability evaluation exercise that is currently being undertaken by NERC. This covers its 35 former Services and Facilities, including the MSTRF. The stated aim of the exercise is simply to establish whether the facilities are actually achieving their stated aims. The results of the evaluation will be used to determine which of the facilities will be invited to apply for funding renewal at the end of the 2016/2017 year. The time scale allowed for the current exercise is very short. The facility documents must be submitted by 17th February 2016 and the evaluation committee will meet in March.

CB questioned what would happen if NERC discontinued funding for the Facility. The Met Office currently relies on wind data from the MST radar to fill a geographical gap in their upper air measurement network. GV responded that it was important for the Met Office to be aware that this threat existed. He thought that the MST radar's operations were better suited to the NERC category of long-term science than to the facility category. However, there was no additional money available through this alternative category.

In other news, DAH reported that the "chemtrail" conspiracy theory had become sufficiently widespread for it to be mentioned by the mainstream media. George Monbiot, writing in *The Guardian*, had bemoaned the fact that it was distracting attention from the real issues of aviation: <http://tinyurl.com/hvt88xm>.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

DAH reported that new NASA-Ames products files and quick-look plots have not been made available since he was obliged to move his operational software onto the jasmin platform in August 2015. He is still in the process of adapting and updating the software. DAH acknowledged that without access to the quick-look plots, he was unable to spot when the tipping bucket rain gauge had become blocked. There was a general discussion about how best to identify when instruments were not working as expected. GV stated that this was an issue that needed to be looked at by the wider NCAS community. He felt that it was better to release the data first and then to worry about flagging up problems. The alternative is to only release data after checks had been carried out.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

The creation of NASA-Ames data files and quick-look plots is now working on the jasmin platform. DAH drew attention to the fact that he had slightly changed the style of the plots. Of particular significance is the way in which the software now wraps cyclic data such as wind direction. Previously the plot line would sweep across the entire y axis range when directions changed from one side of North to the other. Moreover, in the new style plots the direction is shown as 180° when the wind speed drops to zero and the direction is undefined. This helps to differentiate between periods of low wind speed from those when no data were recorded, which are simply identified by a gap in the data. GAP thought it would be better to set the undefined direction values to 0° and/or to hatch out periods of missing data.

He thought that either way, the treatment of such data should be documented.

No data were downloaded from the Frongoch logger between 15th and 18th August 2015. Since the logger can only store approximately two and a half days' worth of data before overwriting, this resulted in the loss of a few hours of data.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

Data files and quick-look plots for this instrument are not yet being created on the jasmin platform.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

DAH noted that he will need to solve a timing issue before he restarts the feed of cloud base files to CEDA. The time stamps in the raw data messages are produced by the instrument's free-running clock, which is prone to drift. DAH had previously dealt with this issue by occasionally manually updating an offset time in the NASA-Ames file creation software. However, the effectiveness of such a solution is limited by human conscientiousness/laziness. An automatic method is required. DAH plans to make the backscatter data available once this issue has been resolved.

GV suggested that DAH should consider replacing the LD40, which is nearly 10 years old and which has been discontinued by Vaisala. He suggested that DAH should speak to Judith Jeffery, who has recently gone through the process of selecting a new model for Chilbolton. DK commented that the lidar/ceilometer manufacturer Jenoptik has recently been taken over by Lufft. GV also suggested that it would be good to relocate Chilbolton's old Halo lidar to Capel Dewi.

4e) Sky-camera

DAH drew attention to a poster of sky-camera images that he had originally created for a RAL Open Day in July 2015. He subsequently added some explanatory notes and published it as an educational resource in December 2015 through the CEDA document repository - <http://cedadocs.badc.rl.ac.uk/1259/>. The resource is covered by a Creative Commons Attribution license, which allows people to print, display, and distribute copies, and to modify the original as long as they credit it - <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Images from the new sky camera will be made available as soon as DAH has determined its pointing direction. He can then embed this and other metadata within the images using a software tool that he has developed for images taken by the NLC camera - see next section.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

DAH has developed software for automatically embedding metadata within image files. This is based on the exiftool software, which is commonly included within Linux distributions and which is available for Windows. The Dublin Core metadata scheme defines 15 general-purpose elements, which can be applied to a wide variety of resources. DAH has used these to describe how, where, when, why, and by whom the NLC camera images were taken. The images would otherwise have had to rely solely on the CEDA file naming convention, which only allows a subset of this information to be recorded. Although Windows-based image viewers, such as Windows Photo Viewer, tend to reveal only a subset of the available metadata (e.g. by right-clicking on an image and selecting "Properties"), Linux software is typically much better. DAH has used the same software to embed metadata within the new-style quick-look plots for MST Radar and Campbell Scientific surface wind data.

4g) MST Radar

CB presented model-comparison statistics for MST radar wind data over recent months. She started with the EUCOS statistics. Availability of data has generally been good, although there have been sporadic days with significantly reduced counts. It's not clear why both the availability and the timeliness were reduced (albeit within expected limits) during April 2015. The daily Root Mean Square (RMS) wind

vector difference values have mostly been below the 5 m s^{-1} target. As expected, the RMS direction difference values show more variability. The Met Office UKV statistics have been good and show no notable change since the previous reporting period. The typical radar wind speed bias - slightly positive in the troposphere and slightly negative in the stratosphere - was less noticeable during September and October 2015 than during November and December. CG commented that data from the South Uist radar showed a different pattern with only the high mode showing a speed bias.

DAH took over reporting for the remainder of this section. He drew attention to the fact that the new style MST radar (st-mode) plots use (nominally) 30 minute averaged horizontal winds for the wind speed, wind shear, and corrected spectral widths. This takes advantage of the improved understanding of the representativeness of the data from recent work carried out by DAH.

The transmitter for antenna sector A automatically shut down on a large number of occasions, between July and November 2015, owing to the final heater voltage dropping below the minimum permissible value. This causes an "analogue error". Although the transmitter can be remotely restarted under such conditions, it does not typically remain in operation for long before the problem recurs. LD changed the transmitter's voltage regulator on 26th August 2015. Nevertheless, the problem recurred several more times during September and October. It hasn't recurred since LD carried out further maintenance on the radar on 3rd November 2015.

The transmitter for antenna sector B was out of action owing a blown fuse on many occasions over the past six months - particularly in July and September 2015. The transmitter for antenna sector C was only out of action on 3 occasions. In each case a blown fuse was responsible. The transmitter for antenna sector D was out of action on a number of occasions on October 12th and on November 4th/5th 2015 owing to the final heater voltage dropping below the minimum permissible value.

Beam steering unit 11 reported elevated VSWR (Voltage Standing Wave Ratio) values on a number of occasions during July and early August 2015. LD replaced the unit on 4th August. He replaced unit 68 on 11th September since its readings were getting close to the permissible limits. Units 69 and 56 became unresponsive on a number of occasions between 1st and 3rd October. Unit 73 was replaced on 15th October, after reporting a low supply voltage on a few occasions during the previous week.

The connection between the radar control and the beam steering PCs was unexpectedly broken at 08:54 UT on 21st August 2015. This led to an increase in the duration of the current cycle by approximately 5 minutes.

5. Guest Instrument Report

Emily Norton was unable to be at the meeting since she was in the process of setting up the Boundary Layer Wind Profiler (BLWP) at Heathrow Airport. This is part of a medium term deployment through the Met Office. DAH showed some pictures of the BLWP that Emily had sent him the previous day. GV reported that at the end of the current deployment, the BLWP will move back to Capel Dewi rather than to Cardington, where it has spent most of its time in recent years.

HMAR gave a report on the lidars. The Elight instrument is now producing laser light after having being out of action for most of the past 2 years. There had been problems with water getting into the high voltage circuits. It is hoped to upgrade the lidar to detect Nitrogen Raman scattering. This would make use of the existing laser. GV added that the water vapour lidar is working well. However, relatively few observations were made in 2015, during the autumn in particular, owing to the preponderance of cloudy conditions. The SAOZ (ozone) instrument was sent back to France for repairs, but is now in working order. A postdoc at Manchester is analysing the data through funding from Defra.

GV is still waiting to hear whether he has funding for the forthcoming international North Atlantic Waveguide and Downstream Impact Experiment (NAWDEX). This will be conducted during September and October 2016 with the aim of quantifying the impact of diabatic processes on the jet stream. Irrespective of the outcome of the grant application, NCAS will be supporting the campaign by making downstream observations.

CB and DK reported that they had both attended the E-PROFILE meeting in late 2015. This programme covers ceilometers/lidars as well as wind-profiling radars. One of the topics discussed was life cycle management of wind profiling radars. The Japanese had replaced the 30+ instruments in their network after approximately 13 years of operation. This raised the question of how to deal with aging instruments within the European network. It was recognised that wind profiler data had a significant impact on the models. It turns out that the demise of the US network was not the result of technical issues or of a lack of interest in the data. CB reported that the Met Office is currently considering what to do with their own profilers. They still have the potential to be operated for a number of years although they will require investment.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) On the use of spectral width - CG

CG has been looking at spectral width data from the Met Office's BLWPs with the intention of establishing whether they contain any useful turbulence information. Based on the assumption of no wind shear and no vertical wind, the beam broadening contribution to the observed spectral width should be very similar irrespective of whether a vertical or 15° off-vertical beam is used. For off-vertical beams, there is expected to be a slight azimuthal dependency whose magnitude depends on the vertical velocity. Shear broadening only affects the off-vertical beams. However, it is a relatively minor contribution.

Looking at 1 year's worth of data from the Camborne BLWP, which has a half-power beam with of 6.3°, it is clear that beam broadening component is the dominant contribution to the observed spectral width. There is a broad correlation between the corrected widths for the two orthogonal off-vertical beams. In some case studies, CG saw broader corrected widths prior to a rain event than following it. DAH reminded CG of Chris Lee's warning to avoid precipitation conditions, since the software might not separate clear air and hydrometeor echoes.

CG is separately interested in the large time variability sometimes seen in BLWP signal parameters. She had previously made a statistical comparison of signal to noise ratios and found that there was a negative bias of approximately 3 dB for the vertical beam values compared to the off-vertical beam values. She wondered if this might be a result of the clutter removal algorithm in the case of the vertical beam observations. She wondered whether the variability in vertical velocities could be used to derive the Brunt-Vaisala frequency for altitudes above the top of the boundary layer.

6b) Raman Lidar- GV

The Raman lidar relies on a 355 nm Nd-Yag laser, which is transmitted vertically into the atmosphere. Optical filters in the return path separate the light for aerosol (355 nm), nitrogen (387 nm), and water vapour (407 nm). During recent summers there has been lots of free tropospheric aerosol. For example, the enhanced aerosol levels observed on 22nd July 2014 were thought to have originated from wild fires in Canada almost a week earlier. Zoe Bradley, a summer student, carried out an analysis of the lidar data with reference to back trajectories. She found that the majority of trajectories for aerosol days had originated over the Canadian hot spots, whereas the majority for non-aerosol days had not.

GV finished by taking a look at data from the Met Office's Raman lidar at Camborne. They had purchased this to aid their volcanic ash work. GV thought that the instrument was giving impressively good signals. In principle it should be possible to estimate the static stability from the backscatter signals.

7. Any Other Business

LD reported that he had heard that Prof Lance Thomas, who had been responsible for setting up the NERC MSTRF, had passed away recently.

The date of the next Experimenters' meeting was provisionally set for the 3rd or 4th week of June 2016. The Radar Advisory Group, i.e. the new steering committee overseeing NERC's atmospheric radars, will be meeting around the same time. The NCAS/Royal Meteorological Society's conference on high impact weather is being held 6th - 8th July in Manchester.